

THE MAGIC BEHIND THE MOUSE: AN INTERDISCIPLINARY ANALYSIS OF DISNEY'S
BEST PRACTICES AND ITS POTENTIAL TO IMPROVE HEALTHCARE

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to understand the aspects and factors of the Disney company that make it one of the most well-known and well-loved companies to date. After understanding these key aspects, an interdisciplinary analysis was done to connect these factors into improving the healthcare industry. An anonymous, virtual interview form was posted to social media to reach a random sample of 82 people. Once initial research was conducted and the interview forum closed, the responses were analyzed, and strong connections were formed between the interview results and the currently published literature. When analyzing the foundational aspects of the company, the theme parks, the Disney community, and the customer service policies, I found that the major sources of Disney's magic include a customer-first ideology, consistency and communication, and community establishment. By knowing these themes that make the Disney company so successful, integrative suggestions were posed to encourage adoption of these aspects into healthcare to build a better, more magical and patient-centered healthcare system. The Disney company positively impacts people daily; by knowing and understanding the root of this magic and integrating those aspects into our current practices as my research suggests, healthcare professionals and the overall healthcare system can become more positively impactful and influential as well.

Introduction

Disney is among one of the most well-known and established companies in the world. Many of us know it from their movies, beloved characters created through the animation studio, or the Disneyland theme parks that can be found worldwide. Many people, including myself, love and adore Disneyland and truly believe that it is the “Happiest Place on Earth” and that the company and its products create a magical atmosphere. Not only does Disneyland allow us to escape the realities of today, but the park fun goes even further by allowing us to transport and enter the lands of yesterday, tomorrow, and fantasy as well.

Since as long as I can remember, Disneyland has been a utopia for me. It is the go-to destination for all family vacations, it was the one place that I was willing to skip a day of school for, and it quickly became my happy place when I needed it most. Not only did it quickly become a love for me, but it was also a love for many of my family members as well. Mainly stemming from my mother, sister, and grandparents, the love for the parks and the mouse became a universal and uniting theme in my household.

While Disneyland can seem like a place that is made and utilized to serve and entertain kids, I did not, and still have not, grown out of my love for Disney. Therefore, when I decided to attend California State University, Fullerton for my undergraduate studies, which happened to be a 14-21 minute drive to Disneyland (depending on traffic), not many people were surprised. Contrary to popular belief, I did not choose to attend CSUF because of its proximity to Disneyland, but it has certainly become a plus and a highlight during my 4 years of higher education. As a result of this very short distance between school and my happy place, I have been fortunate enough to continue spending time in the lands of yesterday, tomorrow, and

fantasy, and my love for them has continued to grow. Thus, as I began to brainstorm and celebrate on what to research for my Senior Honors Project, it seemed only fitting that this passion of mine was included.

However, one thing that I love just as much as Disney is life itself. No, literally. The study of life and all of its moving parts has always been incredibly fascinating to me, which is why I am majoring in Biological Sciences and minoring in Chemistry and Kinesiology while at CSUF. Not only that, but science has become a second language to me and inspired me to pursue and dedicate my own life to maintaining and helping other lives as a future physician. So with these two extreme passions in mind, I ran into a roadblock when deciding on a research topic. Both Disney and science hold exponential value in my life and provide me with a sense of joy and purpose that other topics cannot seem to surpass. So, the issue was deciding which topic I wanted to further research and include to make this an impactful, yet enjoyable project.

I was incredibly fortunate at this point in time to be enrolled in a Women in American Society studies class with Professor Andi Stein at CSUF. In this class, we spoke about incredible, fascinating women within American history that paved the way for so many women of today and how they not only exceeded the social limits placed upon them, but created their own legacies and rulebooks on how to live their best lives. So, as I left one particular lecture from this course feeling liberated and proud to be a woman in STEM, I decided to write my own rulebook about this project: why choose one topic when I can do both? As a result, the inspiration and idea for this project was born.

Through this project, I hoped to explore and discover the aspects of the Disney company that people enjoy and appreciate the most. I hoped to understand and recognize how this company has become so successful in establishing a loyal and loving customer base and how that

strong relationship is maintained. Once that information was discovered, I wanted to connect that newly acquired information and apply it to healthcare. As an individual who has dedicated the last four years studying and researching science and its branches, such as medicine, I have found that there is room for improvement in making healthcare more accessible, equitable, and just within our society. With that in mind, I aimed to connect the factors that allow Disneyland to truly cultivate an atmosphere of magic and discuss why it is important to learn about successful companies and experiences such as Disney. I then wanted to tie these findings into incorporating some of the aspects that make Disney so magical into healthcare-related activities, like going to the doctor or the dentist. I truly believe that if companies and health professions could incorporate and find ways to make their doctor-patient interactions or procedures just a little more magical, it's possible that health-related anxieties or a willingness to access healthcare could improve.

Making healthcare or diminishing barriers towards medical care and procedures cannot happen overnight or from one thesis project. Obviously, we can't put theme parks in hospitals or roller coasters in dental offices, but there are small steps and policies that Disney employs that could make healthcare more accessible and enjoyable, too. If we as a community could identify positive and proven steps that make large companies or organizations like Disney more successful in providing for target audiences, and we employed those strategies in healthcare, it's possible that little-by-little, those barriers could decrease. That is what I hope to achieve with this project: an awareness of how to bring just a little bit of magic to an incredibly significant cause.

Purpose of Project

This project was an analytical study on the aspects of the Disney Company, including its animation studio, theme parks, and additional nuances, such as Disney+. In addition to the analytical research methods utilized, several random, virtual interviews were conducted via online forms that were posted on social media. The responders to these forms were kept completely anonymous, and participation was done completely voluntarily. Lastly, a small-scale study into some of the barriers of healthcare was also completed. The purpose of this project was to gain a better understanding of the factors that truly create the magic within the Disney company, to acknowledge and recognize some of the barriers and current issues within healthcare, and to draw conclusions and connections between those two topics to propose strategies to make healthcare more accessible, approachable, and magical as a whole.

The research conducted regarding the main aspects of Disney and current barriers to healthcare were found and analyzed from already published literature. The questions asked in the virtual interview forms included a rating scale of most commonly appreciated aspects of Disney, a rating scale of common experiences within healthcare, and a fill-in-the-blank section to address other aspects or comments that were not previously mentioned. These questions provided great insight into what real people currently think about both Disney and their experiences receiving healthcare and became the basis for this project.

Methods

In total, there were 82 random and anonymous participants that were surveyed for the main data portion of this study. A Google Form was posted to the social forum of Instagram and was available for anyone to click on. The survey was completely anonymous and was advertised as such to those interested in participating. In order to avoid double counting or confounding variables that could skew the data results, I set the form to only allow one response per click on the link so that one individual could not submit a second response after submitting the first. However, I ensured that no emails or personal data or identifiers were collected with any of the responses.

Each survey responder was asked the same ten questions, and the form was not altered after publication in any way. The questionnaire included six questions that related to the Disney company and four questions that were related to healthcare. All questions were set so that an answer was not required. This was done in order to respect participant privacy and to allow surveyors to skip any questions that either did not apply to them or that they did not feel comfortable answering. The survey remained open from 12/01/2021 to 12/03/2021.

After the 72 hours was completed, the form was deactivated to no longer accept any responses. The Google Forms platform automatically compiles the results from the survey into entire sample data and individual response data. I decided to utilize the entire sample data for this study as it was more comprehensive than looking at all 82 responses individually and would give a better individual on the average opinion and answers to each question.

Once compiled and fully collected, I analyzed the results and made note of which questions would correspond and shed light on the different aspects being analyzed in this paper:

building the company, theme parks and their attractions, fandom and community, and customer service attitudes and policies. Once properly sorted, the sample results were analyzed in comparison to the current literature published, and conclusions were drawn based on those parallels or juxtapositions. Lastly, the conclusions made were then analyzed through a healthcare lens, and the significance of the results and study as a whole was addressed. The next section gives a brief synopsis of the results followed by an in-depth analysis of the results and review of the current literature.

Results

Disney Related Questions

1. Have you ever been to any of the Disneyland Parks?

78 out of 82 participants selected yes (95.1%). 4 out of 82 participants selected no (4.9%).

2. If you have been to the Disneyland Parks before, which of the following aspects positively contributed to your time there?

a. Character Experience (Meet and Greets, Parades, Shows, etc.)

35 out of 77 participants selected this option (45.5%).

b. Attractions/Rides

69 out of 77 participants selected this option (89.6%).

c. Customer Service of Cast Members

38 out of 77 participants selected this option (49.4%).

d. Overall Theme Park Environment (Park Layout, Design, Music, Smell, etc.)

71 out of 77 participants selected this option (92.2%).

3. Which of the following do you believe contributes most positively to the Disney Company overall?

a. Disney+

19 out of 81 participants selected this option (23.5%).

b. Disney Animation Studio (characters, movies, etc.)

60 out of 81 participants selected this option (74.1%).

c. Disneyland Theme Parks

51 out of 81 participants selected this option (63%).

d. The Customer Service/Policies of the Company

11 out of 81 participants selected this option (13.6%).

4. Please select all of the following that apply to you.

a. Have visited a Disneyland theme park

78 out of 81 participants selected this option (96.3%).

b. Have streamed off of the Disney+ service

76 out of 81 participants selected this option (93.8%).

c. Has a favorite Disney character/movie

74 out of 81 participants selected this option (91.4%).

5. In general, how strongly do you believe customer service plays a role in your experience in any activity or at any place?

a. Scale of 0 to 5, 0 being not important at all and 5 being extremely important.

0% of participants selected 0 on the scale.

0% of participants selected 1 on the scale.

1.2% of participants selected 2 on the scale.

8.5% of participants selected 3 on the scale.

24.4% of participants selected 4 on the scale.

65.9% of participants selected 5 on the scale.

6. From the times you have utilized a service from the Disney franchise, how often did you have a positive experience?

a. Almost never

1.3% of the participants selected this option.

b. About 50% of the time

7.5% of the participants selected this option.

c. Almost always

91.3% of the participants selected this option.

Healthcare Related Questions

7. Have you been to see a healthcare professional (doctor, dentist, optometrist, etc.) within the last year?

92.7% of the participants selected yes. 7.3% of the participants selected no.

8. When receiving healthcare services (i.e. screenings, procedures, check-ups), how often do you feel nervous, anxious, or uncomfortable?

a. Almost never

28% of the participants selected this option.

b. About 50% of the time

51.2% of the participants selected this option.

c. Almost always

20.7% of the participants selected this option.

9. Please select any of the following statements that apply to you.

a. I receive health screenings on a regular basis to prevent getting sick

30.5% of the participants selected this option.

b. I only go to healthcare providers when I am sick or need to

74.4% of the participants selected this option.

c. I try to avoid the doctor/dental offices as much as possible

15.9% of the participants selected this option.

10. During the last time you received a healthcare service, did you experience any of the following? Please select all that apply.

a. Good, welcoming customer service

70% of the participants selected this option.

b. A clear debrief/description of the service you were receiving

75% of the participants selected this option.

c. A lack of understanding about the procedures/policies being utilized

22.5% of the participants selected this option.

d. Any form of bias or discrimination

10% of the participants selected this option.

These results were analyzed in comparison to the current literature in the following section.

Literature Review and Analysis

Aspect 1: Building the Company

One of the most groundbreaking and inspiring aspects of Disney is the foundational story behind the making of the company. Founder and creator, Walt Disney, began this journey as an imaginative child who drew illustrations and drawings in his free time. His hobby quickly turned into a passion, and animation became a dream of his. After facing several setbacks and obstacles, such as his own animation studio, Laugh-O-Gram, going bankrupt and facing criticism and skepticism from onlookers, Walt and his brother moved to Los Angeles, California and began a fresh start (Onion, et. al, 2019). Once there, his career really started to take off, especially in 1937 when *Snow White and the Seven Dwarfs* debuted. It was a complete hit that truly lofted the Disney company off the ground. Since then, the company has only grown with more animators, more buildings, and more ideas to bring to life.

An important steppingstone for the Disney Corporation was not only finding and mastering the technology and trade necessary to make animation, but to create masterpieces that truly speak to people. Of course, this process takes time and an incredible mindset; however, throughout the years, the Disney Animation Studio has taken leaps and bounds in making components of their films and creations more appealing to audiences, especially emotionally. In a paper written by Josef Chytry, he proposed that the reason Disney's films have become so successful was due to the "psychological reassurance associated with varying states of self-fulfillment as happiness" (Chytry, 2012). Chytry believes one major reason that the animation studio was able to begin cultivating films and shorts that served as emotional catalysts was because of the pride that went into building the animation academy itself. Described as an animation utopia, the Burbank and Hyperion Studios were immaculate, colorfully designed, and

resembled spaces and buildings only found on Ivy League College Campuses (Chytry, 2012). By creating an immersive, welcoming, and extraordinary space to work, extraordinary products were able to come alive. This same idea was later translated into the making of Disneyland, fusing both the emotion-creating environment and his studio work, but that will be discussed later on.

As a result, it seems that taking the time to ensure the studios and working environments were created in a way to prompt influential and invoking work that was not only worthwhile, but incredibly important for the studio's success. After several developmental years and after the success of his first major film, *Snow White and the Seven Dwarfs*, many of Disney's works continued to play on emotion and established a connection between the characters and the audience. Although targeted for children whose developing minds were more likely to be influenced, his works continued to portray themes of happiness, overcoming obstacles, and nurturance to not only create that connection with children to express a moral, but to rekindle those nostalgic moments within watching adults as well (Chytry, 2012).

With the initial workings and foundational expectation that the work not only needs to be creative and appealing, but now emotion-evoking and influential, the animation studio has had its work cut out for it to continue being at the front lines in animation creation. Although challenging to keep this expectation and prestige alive, with the incredible advances in technology we have seen in recent years, Disney has continued to stay up to date and utilized these new technologies to produce even more memorable work.

Based on an article written by Alisa Alering, the technology needed to keep up with the times has quickly advanced. She mentions that designing in Photoshop and creating two-dimensional images is no longer enough; three-dimensional imaging is where the field is currently at. With this in mind, the complexity of designing several aspects of an image and

having each part come together to contribute to the whole picture in even just one scene can take hundreds of hours (Alering, 2016). She provides the example of Moana; Moana required extreme detail. Each scene had an island background with crashing waves, the sky in the back, trees swaying in the wind, and characters expressing themselves while constantly moving. Alering mentions that years ago scenes of this complex would have taken years to complete; however, with the advancements made in technology thus far, each scene from the movie took approximately 12 hours to complete, give or take (Alering, 2016).

Although the time commitment to produce these images has certainly lessened from what it was in the past, the rewards have skyrocketed. Moana has quickly become a fan-favorite character and brought in \$81 million dollars to the box office upon its release in the theaters (Alering, 2016). This extreme success was not just due to the technology allowing beautiful images of the ocean to be seen, but because the animators at Disney studio have created an expectation and dedication to using these tools to create meaningful characters with even more meaningful stories. The things we see on the screen allow us to transport and explore new worlds and adventures that we wouldn't be on without these scenes. This personal connection has become one of Disney's greatest strengths and something that several other researchers have noticed as well.

Although there are several answers out there as to why so many people love Disney, a huge reason that continuously appears is how the Disney movies make people feel. According to articles by Beverly Devakishen and another by Kaitlin Miller, the aesthetic Disney provides is not only relatable, but can be so individualized and specific that audiences cannot help but connect. Especially with movies such as Hercules, Emperor's New Groove, and Lion King as examples, these movies have very different story lines that are unique and specific to different

things; however, there are still similar underlying morals and themes. In some cases, the thrilling seek of adventure and dreams allows viewers to connect to the movies and feel like a kid again. In other scenarios, when the protagonists make mistakes, but we still view them as good, strong characters with good intentions and a virtuous heart, we relate to the forgiveness we should give ourselves when we make our own mistakes (Devakishen, 2021). The love and friendship created in the movies and films reminds us of our love in our lives and creates an invisible bond and connection between us and these characters and films (Miller, 2016). With all of these aspects in mind, the main idea is that Disney's animation works to allow viewers to feel. Whether it's the music, the bond amongst characters, the scenery, or just the feeling of accomplishment or victory found at the end of most films, these factors bring out more emotion and feeling in those watching. That is a true magic of Disney: a creation of feeling that makes viewers not only want to get out there and explore and chase their own dreams, but to express more love and feeling of their own as well (Miller, 2016). One last aspect from Devakishen's article that is greatly supported amongst other Disney animation research is that in nearly every film, a change for the better tends to occur. While this may seem small or like a given, this aspect is incredibly important because it instills a hope in viewers that a change for the better in our world could be possible too, and that's an exceedingly impactful thought to hold onto during these crazy lives of ours that allow Disney watchers and lovers to leave the theater feeling inspired every time (Devakishen, 2021).

Applicable Data

When conducting my own research, I found several overlapping results to the findings discussed above. Below are the interview questions pertaining to this section and the related results.

If you have been to the Disneyland Parks before, which of the following aspects positively contributed to your time there?

Out of 75 responses, 34 respondents said that character experiences at the parks such as meet and greets, parades, or shows positively contributed to their time while being there. This is an important piece of data because all of the character experiences at Disneyland are based and founded on the animation studio. Thus, when visitors are at the parks and have the opportunity to meet and interact with characters they've seen in the movies and films, they are more likely to have a positive experience. This not only shows how the animation studio's characters and creations can leave a lasting impression on viewers, but how consistently exposing audiences to these characters can continue building that relationship and bringing enjoyable experiences to viewers in various ways.

Which of the following do you believe contributes most positively to the Disney Company overall?

Out of options that included Disney+, the Disney animation studio (characters, movies, etc.), Disneyland theme parks, and the customer service/policies of the company, 58 out of 79 respondents concluded that the Disney animation studio most positively contributes to the company overall. Given that 73% of people responded this way, it's clear that the animation studio is what makes Disney the company that it is. Although Disney has expanded into theme

parks and streaming services, the impact the studio made when it first opened in 1923 is continuing to this day. The studio's creations clearly allow fans and audiences to connect with its creations and are a main factor that keeps people coming back and continuing to have positive experiences with the company.

Please select all of the following that apply to you: I have visited a Disneyland theme park, I have streamed off of the Disney+ service, and/or I have a favorite Disney character/movie.

Out of the 79 responses, 73 people, or 92% selected that they did have a favorite Disney character or movie. Although this may seem like a silly finding, it shows that when not prompted with specific movies or characters, but simply asked if they had a favorite character, 92% of people could remember or think of a character or movie from Disney that left some sort of positive mark on their life. This further validates the current research and literature out there that the Disney animation studio does indeed create or facilitate some sort of emotional connection with its audiences. This is because if it hadn't, not as many respondents would be able to recall or identify a character that has become their favorite.

With all of these results from the anonymous interviews in mind, the Disney animation studio does play a huge role in the company's success and impact. I believe it is safe to say that without the work of the animation studio, the company would not be what it is today. However, even more important than the movies or characters themselves, is the emotional and personal connection the animation studio has fostered. This connection allows audiences to continue to feel connected to a specific movie or creation even when without examples and resultantly

allows them to enjoy other aspects of the company even further due to this foundational and significant connection.

Aspect 2: Theme Parks and Their Attractions

While Disney's animation studio is one of the most noteworthy and memorable aspects to the Disney company, arguably the second most popular is the Disney theme parks. With 12 parks and nine resorts, Disney has expanded its influence from magic on screens to an in-person magical experience on its own.

Walt's idea to build a theme park began early on in his career and really took shape from his early memories at a nice, well-kept park in Kansas City called Electric Park. His early childhood memories from this park and the glorious lights and enchanting excitement that it created produced a lasting inspiration for the way he wanted Disneyland to be. However, it wasn't until sitting on a bench at Griffith Park in Los Angeles and watching the kids have fun on the merry-go-round, riding the train, or exploring on the river boats that Walt became serious and created a clearer vision for his park (Denney, 2017).

From there, his idea of a main street that connected to a wild wilderness frontier that was encircled by a train that overlooked a riverboat front took hold. Continuing to work with animators and production designers like Dick Kelsey, Disneyland was created and officially opened on July 17th, 1955 (Denney, 2017).

As a Disneyland lover myself, I can't help but wonder if Walt truly knew the impact he was leaving when creating Disneyland. Knowing that the goal was to create the "Happiest Place on Earth", it's safe to say he definitely created a one-of-a-kind experience that allows people to leave feeling even happier than when they arrived.

An article written by David Allen describes this feeling and how Disney achieves this experience and related emotions as a new sense of reality. The fantasy aspect of Disneyland appears and begins from start to finish; from the moment you enter the park to the corners of

each land. As soon as you step into Disneyland and begin your journey down Main Street, you observe vintage-looking buildings with shining lights that look real but are more enchanting and welcoming than they would be in person (Allen, 2014). The stores that border the street are smaller and more to scale to not only create that private, new-world type of feel, but to give off that toy-like, fantasy vibe as well. This correlation and juxtaposition between real life elements turned fantastical or magical continues throughout every inch of the park. Allen gives the example of the ride The Jungle Cruise. On this ride, passengers board a real boat that sails through real water to look at animals and tropical scenes that many know are not truly alive. However, the commitment towards the animatronics, the skipper manning the ship through the waters, and the passengers' willingness to believe in the simulation creates a hyperreal illusion for both adults and kids to enjoy. This illusion is said to be an "extension of the cinema" (Allen, 2014). It's the ideas and scenes from the animation studio turned to life through this mixture and collision of real and fantasy.

Although many visitors, especially the adults at the parks, understand that these rides and attractions are simply just that: mechanical rides, the emotional connection towards the characters and movies combined with the real aspects of the lands allow even the adults to escape the reality of the world during their visit and fall into the fantasy and magic of the parks.

Similar to the realness of the rides creating a whole new world for guests to enjoy, there are several other aspects of the parks that transport guests into a new reality and allow them to feel more connected to the park. In an article by Charles Carson, the utilization of music as a vessel to connect with fans and guests is discussed. Carson explains how music and soundtracks are an integral part of the Disney animation studio's creations and how the use of music is also carried over into the parks (Carson, 2004).

Upon entering the theme parks, even while going through security, music is played overhead and throughout the shops. These songs are ones from Disney's work that is not only recognizable but allow visitors to feel a sense of nostalgia from previous loved movies watched and to create new memories associated with this music while inside the park. Not only that, but live music performances by real performers also fill the parks. The use of live performers, such as the barbershop quartet or the live band that marches down Main Street, is to entertain the audience and to once again bring to life the classic animation soundtracks that many have come to know and love (Carson, 2004).

Similarly, Carson explains how music throughout the parks helps set the scene to further transport guests from reality into fantasy. In Frontierland, western, country music is played to set the scene. At Disney World in EPCOT, each section or pavilion represents a different place with different music. For example, in the Mexico pavilion, mariachi bands and Aztec and Mayan songs and dances are performed. Similar to the experience on rides like The Jungle Cruise, the guests allow themselves to believe in the simulations even when they know things aren't real and allow themselves to believe in the fantasy and magic presented to them. The same submission to the dream also takes place when surrounded by music. This creates an authentic experience that allows guests to relate and connect to the area and the performances, allowing them to reminisce and remember their own lives in a nostalgic and happy way. When the guests allow themselves to believe in the Disney portrayals of their cultures, of their lives, and of the real-life elements in front of them, they begin to adopt this colorful and upbeat rendition and are left with that positive sentimentality (Carson, 2004).

One other noteworthy element to the Disneyland theme parks that has been linked to the overall experience of park-goers would be the smells present throughout the park and the rides

themselves. According to much research out there, the sense of smell creates the strongest link to memory out of all the senses (Hamer, 2019). Thus, when a highly distinct smell is produced over and over again, we begin to draw connections and associations with those smells that we can recall easily. An article by Gavin Doyle describes the impact smell has on park visitors.

Throughout the entire park and in each ride, small vents are placed to pump out specific scents. Each one is different; for example, the scents outside of the shops on Main Street resemble the food being sold. The popcorn smell from the snack carts travels for miles. The Pirates of the Caribbean ride and the Haunted Mansion ride have scents that correlate to their specific themes (Doyle, 2020). The genius behind this scent incorporation is that it allows guests, especially guests who revisit the parks, to establish a physiological and mental connection with the parks. When we step into the boats on Pirates of the Caribbean, the salty sea smell immediately reminds us of our previous experiences with the ride and establishes a relationship and association with that smell (Doyle, 2020). Likewise, when a guest is walking through Tomorrowland and smells gasoline, they remember and know that the Autopia ride is close by. As a result, whether it be the combination of real and fantasy elements, the music, or the scents, the ambiance and environment of Disney catalyzes associations to be made between the individual and the park, which prompts guests to continue connecting with the company on a personal level and coming back for more.

Bringing all these aspects together, an article by Katie Murar describes an example of just how extraordinary the Disney theme parks can be. In her article, she describes the grand opening of the new Star Wars: Galaxy's Edge land. Opening at the beginning of 2020, the Rise of the Resistance ride became not only one of the most expensive additions to the park but was also one of the most "ambitious [and] immersive attractions" as well (Murar, 2020). One of the most

noteworthy aspect of this addition to the land was that the land's combination of virtual reality and a physical rollercoaster type of feel allowed for connections between all the Star Wars movies to be made and make the overall land more cohesive. The most common comment made about this new attraction upon its opening was just how extravagant of a story is told and how the design allows riders to not even realize the ride has begun when they enter (Murar, 2020). This ride, and the Star Wars: Galaxy's Edge land itself, combines many of the park aspects that make Disneyland unique. The exceptional attention to detail truly allows visitors to enter a galaxy far, far away; the themed music and scents of galaxy-themed snacks that fill each walkway and the rides that follow the movies down to each detail leave a lasting impression on those who ride it.

Star Wars: Galaxy's Edge serves as just one example of the impressive work Disneyland has created to transform the experiences of visitors. Whether it is the scent, the music, or the connection between films and attractions that create a connection between the land and the visitor, it's these elements that allow people to view and experience the Disney magic firsthand.

Applicable Data

In order to better understand and investigate the aspects of the Disneyland park that are recognized and appreciated by people, some of my interview questions alluded to gathering this data. The questions pertaining to this aspect are found below.

Please select all of the following that apply to you: I have visited a Disneyland theme park, I have streamed off of the Disney+ service, and/or I have a favorite Disney character/movie.

With a total of 81 responses to this question, 78 people, or 96.3% of responders answered that they have visited a Disneyland theme park. This was a critical foundational question to ask because since the next few questions are related to the aspects inside the theme parks, it's important to know if the responders have actually witnessed and experienced those elements. Since 96.3% of those who responded have been to the parks, I am confident that the following responses will be accurate opinions and recollections from their experiences. I also believe that since all respondents had the opportunity to not answer questions that did not apply to them, the results for the following questions will not be answered by folks who have never been to the parks. Thus, knowing this information, the results to the next questions will be accurate opinions and a fair representation of how real visitors view and experience the Disneyland theme park.

If you have been to the Disneyland Parks before, which of the following aspects positively contributed to your time there?

Out of the 77 responses, 69 people responded that attractions and rides positively contributed, and 71 people said that the overall theme park environment (park layout, design, music, smell, etc.) also positively impacted their visit. Given that both of these factors had well over 80% of

respondents agreeing positively with these aspects, it's clear that the theme parks and the way they operate do indeed leave a lasting impact on the people who visit them. Without as much detail and immersion within the experience, these results may have been drastically different, and it's possible that fewer people would have such strong opinions about Disneyland and the company as a whole. This data allows us to recognize that the nature of Disneyland and its consistent commitment to providing such a specific and unique experience is what makes it so noteworthy to many individuals.

Which of the following do you believe contributes most positively to the Disney Company overall?

Out of 81 responses, 51 people said that the Disneyland theme parks most positively contribute to the Disney company overall. Although this was not the highest rated answer, it was a close second choice with 63% agreeing that the theme parks are huge factors that make the company so successful. I think this was an important aspect to consider because it really shows how much of a significance the parks leave in the broad scheme of things. Even with other impactful aspects such as good customer service, the animation studio, and streaming services like Disney+, the parks are considered the second largest contributor in this data sample. That being said, it's clear that the techniques Disney currently has in place to ensure visitors have a memorable and enjoyable experience are successful and truly contributing to the positive legacy Walt always hoped for.

With this applicable data in mind, it's safe to conclude that the current literature and research regarding the magic of Disneyland continues to ring true. The overall creation of the parks and the experience they provide for visitors is a factor to write home about and is

noteworthy, according to those surveyed. When compared to several other aspects of the company, the experience at the parks is one that the majority positively supports and believes provides a unique aspect that other companies simply cannot replicate. One of the biggest takeaways here though is simply how consistent Disneyland is. The fact that over 75 individuals can enter the park at different times, days, and potentially even years and experience the same unique level of detail, immersion, and overall magic is incredible. To me, and many others, it's this dedication to staying so consistent with the experience they provide that makes visitors more likely to positively acknowledge these factors and to ultimately come back in the future, too.

Aspect 3: Fandom and Community

From the creation of the animation studio and theme parks, it is clear that a fandom of visitors and supporters has begun to rise. Even from the applicable data that has been analyzed thus far, a vast majority of responders have agreed that they positively view the company or feel connected to it in some way, whether that is through having a favorite movie or character or feeling connected to the soundtrack and theme park experiences. Regardless of the reasoning, the Disney company would certainly not be where it is today without the support and love it receives from fans. This section of research will analyze how this fandom and community of supporters has come to be and how it has grown and maintained itself to be so strong and supportive of the company as a whole.

A current literature article that highlights several key impacts on how the fandom of Disneyland has surfaced is written by David Giles. According to Giles, the foundation of this fandom is due to the aspects of Disneyland previously mentioned, the movies and the parks. These aspects truly make Disney unique and provide that “Disney magic” that you simply cannot get anywhere else. As a result, visitors who recognize these magical and unique aspects of the company are more likely to participate more frequently and deeply, creating a connection and loyalty to the company (Giles, 2017). Jumping off this idea, he looks at three specific instances where fans express their loyalty beyond standard visitors: pin trading, Disneybounding, and connections to attractions.

Giles explains that pin trading is one of the simplest yet most influential aspects of the parks that allow visitors to become more connected and truly begin to identify with Disney as a whole. For example, many fans of Disney tend to buy pins that represent their interests, their personalities, or their favorite characters. As a result, fans can then create sub-communities of

people with similar pins where buying and trading can continue to occur over and over. Giles makes the analogy that Disney pins become a form of body art and expression for visitors. However, most importantly, it serves as a way for fans to not only connect with the park and interact on a deeper level, but to connect and form bonds with one another. Similar to Walt's original vision, this creates harmonious communities of visitors that continue to support one another and allow the company to continue thriving as well (Giles, 2017).

Similar to pins becoming a form of expression, another technique fans are utilizing to express themselves and their love for Disney is the new, popular trend of Disneybounding. Disneybounding is when fans choose normal clothes to wear that when paired together, allow them to resemble a certain character or identity. This is similar to cosplay but without fully recreating a costume. Giles goes on to describe how these disneybounders that represent, or channel, specific Disney characters allow themselves to resemble aspects of Disney that they love while remaining individualistic in who they are. An activity such as this allows guests to feel excited getting ready to go into the theme parks, to create communities with one another to Disneybound together, and to freely express their individuality and love for certain aspects of Disney. Most importantly, Giles notes that the number of fans who participate in activities like this truly shows just how large and how loyal of a fandom Disney really has. The idea that a film or character touches and reaches someone so strongly that they choose to channel that character while visiting the parks reveals how cultivated this fandom really is and how large of a community Disney has created in even the small activities like wearing yellow to resemble Princess Belle (Giles, 2017).

The last aspect that Giles mentions is that many fans of the attractions or theme parks will try to leave personal items or marks on the parks to further their connection to the company as a

whole. For example, many people will leave stickers, pennies, loose change, or other small items to hopefully go unnoticed that they can come find once they visit the parks again. Most noteworthy in Giles' research was in regard to fan connections to the Haunted Mansion. There have been several allegations and rumors that some fans take the invitation to be the 1000th ghost too literally and have tried to leave or spread cremated remains near or on the attraction (Giles, 2017). Obviously, this is not allowed in the park and Disneyland has taken proper precautions to prevent this from occurring; however, Giles believes it's worth mentioning. This is because it truly shows just how deep of a connection fans feel towards the park and the company. He makes that analogy that if you are a music connoisseur, you may want to be buried with your music sheets. If you are a Disney fan, you may want to be buried at your home away from home and the Happiest Place on Earth (Giles, 2017). Giles concludes by saying that all three of these aspects, and especially the extreme of wanting your ashes to remain in the place you love most, show just how strong the community and fandom of Disney truly is and the lengths fans are willing to go to express that love (Giles, 2017).

Another aspect of the company that has become more popular and truly allows a greater and larger community and fandom of Disney to spread is the Disney+ streaming service. Towards the end of 2019, Disney+ was launched and allowed subscribers to watch movies, short films, and series TV shows from the Pixar, Marvel, Star Wars, and Disney universes. According to a paper written by Jordan Sturgill, Disney truly played off the early nostalgia and childhood connections that fans love and enjoy by including movies and films, both old and new, for people of all ages to watch and re-watch (Sturgill, 2019). Additionally, Disney has truly advanced in the way of technologies and utilized these talents and resources to release new Disney+ special shows and series that allow them to continue leading and paving the way in terms of animation

and film. Finally, in a mention to another study, Sturgill sheds light on the fact that Disney remains a company whose films are a “source of authority” in teaching and influence. The extremely loyal customer base that once existed before the launch of Disney+ exponentially grew after its release as well. Since loyal customers who have purchased Disney items or engaged with the company in the past and had a positive experience, these loyal fans were more likely to purchase the Disney+ subscription and really help get this streaming service off the ground. Due to this continually growing fandom, Disney+ has flourished and become a top streaming service of today (Sturgill, 2019).

Another interesting component of Disney+ that really reveals just how much of a community and network it has become is the status of the streaming service during the COVID-19 global pandemic in 2020 that is still ongoing today. According to an article by Ryan Faughnder, the pandemic brought about major losses to the Disney company because the theme parks were forced to close down out of safety for the community. However, despite this major setback for the company, the number of subscribers to Disney+ skyrocketed. By October of 2020, the number of subscribers hit 7.3 million people. Faughnder goes on to describe that Disney+ served as a light and source of hope for many during this unknown and scary time. The launch of several Disney+ original series kept people entertained and connected to the company at a time where the world felt disconnected. Faughnder also notes that this streaming service and the continual releases of new and old films for people to watch and revisit allows people to feel a sense of control in their lives, to remember a simpler and happier time in their lives, and to connect with others who were also utilizing the service (Faughnder, 2020). This article and the sheer number of people utilizing the platform really goes to show the impact Disney+ had on

people and communities during this stressful time and highlights how strong of a fanbase and community Disney truly has and is continuing to form.

Disney+ is a prime example of how the Disney company provides outlets for fandom interaction and community building, even from the comfort of one's own home. The streaming service allows fans to continue loving and experiencing the Disney magic wherever they go and extend their loyalty even more than before. Not only that, but it's outlets like Disney+ that allow the Disney company to be extremely consistent. The company continually provides ways for fans to get the content and experience they want when using a Disney product, and the accessibility of being able to stream the magic from one's cell phone or television not only extends this magic to more communities but allows the fanbase to interact with the company on a more consistent basis, too.

One last example of how the Disney company fosters a loyal fanbase and community is by serving in the community itself. Based on an article by Echo Blickenstaff, another aspect of Disney that makes the company so special is its willingness to spread magic to those in need. According to the article, the company participates and is very vocal about supporting charities and communities in need. For example, upon the opening of the Shanghai Disney Resort, \$3.1 million dollars was donated to create playrooms in children's hospitals all across China. These rooms were then linked with the VoluntEARS program, where cast members and families of those from the company volunteer to play, support, and bring a little bit of magic to these kids in the hospital to brighten their stay or treatments (Blakenstaff, 2018). Similar to the efforts made in China, Disney is extremely involved in the Make-A-Wish Foundation. The company puts in over 200 hours per individual case to ensure that any Disney-related wishes are done to an

extraordinary extent; Disney also created the #ShareYourEars social media campaign to raise money and awareness for children fighting chronic illnesses (Blakenstaff, 2018).

There are several other efforts and campaigns that Disney creates or participates in to support communities across the globe, including chronic illness support, natural disaster and tragedy relief efforts, and more. This is an incredible aspect of the company that often goes undiscussed yet plays a huge role in the reputation of the company. For many fans, seeing a company, especially one as established and financially well-off as Disney, give back to communities in need leaves a strong, positive lasting impression on many and validates and inspires many to continue supporting the company, join the community, and encourage others to do so as well. Most importantly, Disney's collaboration and efforts to support communities brings magic to those who may not have access to it and that consistency and willingness to serve others speaks boldly about the company and truly allows many to continue supporting Disney and the work that the company does as a whole.

Applicable Data

In order to see if the current literature is true about the loyal fanbase and extensive community Disney has created, I am analyzing several applicable questions from my survey to see if these same concepts apply to my random survey of 82 anonymous respondents.

Which of the following do you believe contributes most positively to the Disney Company overall?

Out of 81 participants for this question, 19 people agreed that Disney+ is the factor that contributes the most to the company overall. This question had the select all feature, and the options were Disney+, the Disney Animation Studio (characters, movies, etc.), and the

Disneyland Theme Parks. While the majority of respondents answered that the theme park or animation studio most greatly influenced the company, 19 people still said Disney+ was its most positive feature. This is still a significant result because even compared to an amusement park and an entire franchise of movies and films, 23.5% of responders believed that the streaming service was its more redeeming quality. I think this speaks very highly to not only the quality of work Disney has put in to ensure that their services are worthwhile and impactful but also shows how unifying something as small as a streaming service can be. Seeing that 23.5% of people believe this feature alone gives the company a positive rating really shows how loyal the fanbase is to the movies and films offered by the company. Although this was not the most significantly strong applicable data question, I still believe this reflects the current literature and the impact Disney outlets have on the community.

Please select all of the following that apply to you.

Seventy-six out of 81 participants selected that they have streamed off the Disney+ service. Given that this 93.8% result is much greater than half and represents a wide majority of the respondents, it is clear that this service is definitely being utilized and has reached the community. I think this is an important foundational question and statistic to include because it not only reflects the literature stated above but reveals that the community is continuing to engage with the franchise's work even when they are not inside the theme park. I also think it speaks very highly of the company that with many streaming services available, such as Netflix, Hulu, and Youtube TV, a vast majority of surveyors chose to subscribe to Disney's platform.

From the times you have utilized a service from the Disney franchise, how often did you have a positive experience?

91.3% of the participants selected the “almost always” option. This is a great statistic that I think reflects and parallels the literature and the hypothesis that the Disney community and fanbase is very strong and extensive. To have such a large majority of surveyors agree that they almost always have a positive experience allows us as researchers to see that the influence of Disney is still very much alive.

From these results and the literature analyzed above, I conclude that the positive experiences the majority of surveyors and visitors have with the company allow them to form a connection with Disney that keeps them coming back. As the franchise continues to grow and release new outlets for fans to connect and interact even more, such as the Disney+ service and opportunities to pin trade or Disneybound, fans continue to develop and cherish that bond and thus a loyal community of fans that will continue to come back for more forms. The major takeaway I see from this particular section is how consistent the Disney company is. Their consistency is what I believe makes them such a standout and unique franchise because almost always, visitors and users of Disney services have a positive experience. This consistent result allows them to have faith that these experiences are worth their time and money and thus they willingly choose to come back and support. The numerous opportunities and outlets Disney provides in order to build and foster a sense of community keeps that magic alive in not only a consistent way, but an accessible one, too. It’s these features of the company that I believe are contributing the most to making the company so successful and influential among so many individuals.

Aspect 4: Customer Service Attitudes and Policies

While the previously mentioned aspects of the Disney company are notable and extremely important to the strong and respectable reputation of the company and its organizations, one of its most noteworthy aspects is Disney's customer service.

This aspect has been well-analyzed for several years; for example, in 2000, a study from the University of Tennessee was dedicated to analyzing the globalization of several companies, including Disney. In the study, the strength of customer loyalty, attachment, and beliefs were studied. As a result, it was found that Disney's extensive marketing and advertising creates a high expectation for the experience customers will receive when they engage and interact with the facets of the company. Thus, when customers do have this positive experience, a level of trust and likability of the company is developed. A huge part of this is the customer service that comes into not only supplying the proper advertising for establishing that connection but giving the proper treatment to guests and customers to keep that magic and positive experience alive. The company's willingness to fully commit and support the consumer experience allows many individuals to be able to connect and rely on the company to continue having positive interactions and experiences; therefore, supporting the growth and globalization of the company as a whole (Robbins, 2014).

Likewise, another study done from Liberty University points out crisis management and the company's handling of negativity. On several occasions, the company and their public relations team have worked hard to ensure guests have an unforgettable experience and to adapt and adjust as necessary when an issue arises. For example, in the early years of the Disneyland theme parks, it became apparent that guests would get bored while waiting in long lines and that the cleanliness of the parks was an important factor for guests. As a result, the company began

doing entertainment like parades, live music, and character walk-arounds to provide entertainment near rides with long lines and hired maintenance and a cleaning staff to keep the park clean during the day. It is actions such as these that allow guests, audiences, and onlookers to have such a high respect for the customer service and overall company attitude of Disney (DeMeo, 2014). These actions and other instances have highlighted that the company is customer-focused and willing to make changes to better the experience of their guests when necessary. These aspects continue to keep guests attached and loyal and thus coming back for future visits and engagements as well.

This customer service has several layers that make it so outstanding; it really boils down to the people involved. An article from MedTrade highlighted that the Disney company is a unique company because of how customer-focused it truly is. The article continues to explain that it is able to be this focused because of the people hired and how they are trained. Company analyzer Louis Feuer, states that the company is “represented by hard-working, dedicated professionals” who allow their training to positively shine through when helping guests (Keirn, 2013). Similarly, an article from Travel Pulse agrees that while the movies, characters, and music made by the company are iconic and extraordinary in themselves, it’s the people that make Disney so magical. The cast members, staff, volunteers, animators, and ambassadors bring the magic to life every day and communicate it to guests in a way that is relatable and special. The love these people display for the company becomes contagious and allows guests and audiences to escape from their reality for a little while and feel the same sense of love and magic that employees are feeling (Schottey, 2016).

With all these articles and examples in mind, it’s clear that Disney has done a fantastic job of cultivating teams of staff and cast members that make a difference at the company.

Without these people, there would be no Disney+, Disneyland, Disney movies, or iconic soundtracks. The people behind the scenes, at the front gates, and in studios creating content are the messengers and creators that allow each individual to feel the Disney magic for themselves. Their dedication to ensuring our experiences are nothing short of outstanding is the true backbone of the magic behind Disney.

Applicable Data

To further explore just how much of an impact customer service can play in one's experience at any company, questions regarding this aspect were included in the anonymous survey and are analyzed below.

In general, how strongly do you believe customer service plays a role in your experience in any activity or at any place?

Out of a scale from 0 to 5, 65.9% of respondents chose a 5, indicating that they believe customer service plays a very strong role in their experience at a place. 24.4% of responders chose a 4 out of 5, 8.5% of people said a 3- indicating a moderate strength, and 1.2% chose a 2 out of 5, indicating little correlation between customer service and experience. Since the majority of people did select a very strong correlation between the customer service they receive and the experiences they have, I conclude that it is safe to say that it is an important factor to consider for any company.

With this correlation in mind, I do think Disney's customer service and the customer service of other companies and organizations is a crucial factor to look at when analyzing the work and impact of these places.

If you have been to the Disneyland parks before, which of the following aspects positively contributed to your time there?

49.4% of respondents agreed that the customer service of cast members positively contributed to their time at the parks. Given that almost half of the responses reflect that customer service did make a difference, I believe this reflects the current literature provided that the work being done by the people of Disney do make a difference. Therefore, Disney serves as a prime example that when a company has good customer service and a customer-focused approach, the experiences of its customers as guests may be more positive. I think the result from this question does show an initial association that the customer service provided by Disney is an impactful aspect to the magic provided to guests.

Which of the following do you believe contributes most positively to the Disney company overall?

Out of the choices of Disney+, the Disney Animation Studio, the Disneyland theme parks, and the customer service/policies of the company, 13.6% of respondents chose Disney's customer service as the most positive contributing factor. Although this percentage is lower than the other options, I still find it significant that compared to a theme park and one of the most noteworthy animation studios, 11 responders still believe customer service is the most important aspect. This is great evidence that customer service can leave a lasting impression and it has for the Disney company.

These results prove to me that while customer service may not be the most talked about or overly expressed factor behind the magic of Disney, it is certainly a necessary piece to the entire puzzle. The work and training of the people behind Disney certainly does make a difference, even if it appears small. The company serves as an example of the customer service

that keeps people coming back and the type of service expected of companies to keep creating a positive and magical experience on a continual and reliable basis.

Significance: At the Interface of Disney and Medicine

There are several aspects and factors that have been analyzed about the Disney company and that can be translated into healthcare. Many of the same issues, policies, and goals of the theme park are similar to those within the healthcare system, although it may not be obvious. Some of these similarities include wanting to foster an inclusive and welcoming environment, breaking down barriers towards utilizing services, and wanting a healthy and happy experience for visitors and consumers. While each of these factors will be discussed in depth in the following sections, it's important to first consider the direct link between the two topics: how does Disney directly affect someone's health, specifically their mental health?

Direct Association: Mental Health

Based on current literature and research out there already, Disney and its products can play a role in the mental health of those visiting the parks or enjoying their products. For example, in a health podcast hosted by Greg Hamilton, Hamilton describes the findings from a study done in Vienna, Austria. In the study, groups of cancer patients were separated into two groups, one experimental and one control. In the experimental group, the cancer patients watched one of eight specifically chosen Disney movies that were happy and invoked happy feelings while receiving their chemotherapy treatments. In the control group, the patients did not watch any Disney movies while receiving their treatments. After the treatment, the patients from each group completed a questionnaire about how they were doing physically, emotionally, and socially. Based on the results, the study revealed that the patients who watched the Disney movie during treatment felt less fatigued, less weight from current family or social issues, and less

stressed and worried altogether (Hamilton, 2020). This study reveals not only that there may be a direct link between Disney and healthcare, but that the creations from the Disney company can positively affect individuals in several different ways.

Likewise, many other sources display how the Disney Company is making strides in directly influencing mental health. In a personal blog, Annual Passholder Kyle Elliot shares how going to Disneyland so often allows him to make positive changes in his own mental health journey. He notes that Disneyland serves as a place for him to get away from the stress of work for a while, a place for him to be re-inspired about growing and trying new things as an entrepreneur himself, and most importantly, a place for him to be his unique and authentic self. He shares that as a gay man and someone who struggles with an anxiety disorder, Disneyland has become a home for him to relax, let go of his anxiety, and not worry about fitting in or being judged. As a visitor during Disneyland's "Gay Days" celebration, he said he felt welcomed, accepted, and encouraged to be exactly the person that he is. Mr. Elliot serves as a firsthand example of Disney's commitment to providing a welcoming environment for all of its guests that can truly make a difference and even improve one's mental health while visiting, too (Elliot, 2021).

Not only are celebrations such as "Gay Days" making movements to be more inclusive while working to improve individual's mental health, but Disney's policies are also evolving to continue fostering a healthy and happy experience across the board. According to a site dedicated to sharing the accessibility secrets of the Disneyland parks, author Angela Coate shares that Disneyland has a Disability Access Service for guests to utilize to receive accommodations to better their visit while at the parks. More specifically, this service applies to not only guests with physical disabilities, but also those dealing with mental illnesses, chronic illnesses,

cognitive disorders, and autism (Coate, 2021). It's services such as this that allow the Disney company to have a positive effect on mental health. Disney is setting the example that it is not just enough to acknowledge that mental illnesses are prevalent or that an inclusive environment is important, but that action needs to be connected with that recognition to really make a difference.

Lastly, while the Disneyland parks themselves are at the forefront of the correlation between Disney and mental health, the animation studio has also played a large role in addressing the stigmas around mental health and how to manage them. According to a paper published in a psychology journal, a study was done that analyzed how mental illnesses are portrayed in Disney movies. The researcher looked specifically at *Winnie the Pooh* and *Inside Out* to conduct their research. The author found that these Disney movies accurately depict and portray characters that deal with depression, based on the ICD-10 guidelines. This is a critical conclusion made from this research because it allows the audience to know that Disney has done their homework. The writers behind these movies and shows are educated and understand the symptoms and signs of those struggling with mental issues, like depression. Knowing this, it makes these movies an educational tool. For example, Eeyore from *Winnie the Pooh* is known and explored to be a character who displays depressive thoughts and actions. While Eeyore serves as a great symbol and depiction of signs of depression, we also see his group of friends support him despite those signs, encourage him to do things he loves, find ways to make him happy, and still include him as part of the group. Sadness from *Inside Out* is used as another example of a character with depressive tendencies who is still accepted, supported, and loved for who she is. The article continues to explain that by creating an accurate character mold for this illness and continuing to show ways to care for individuals dealing with it, Disney is educating

its audiences on mental illnesses and how to support those living with them. Furthermore, by including characters with real-life characteristics and situations to deal with, it allows these movies to be more relatable and impactful (Caves & Basu-Roy, 2020). Someone who is dealing with depression may have feelings of worthlessness or incapability, but watching Eeyore and Sadness be main characters who make a difference in these movies may allow that individual to see themselves in a different and more positive light than they had before.

All of these pieces of literature and research articles make it clear that Disney can have a direct impact on healthcare issues. Its positive impact on mental health is yet another layer to the magic that the Disney company can provide to its community. While Disney continues to set this prime example in its direct link to health, there are many other ways that the aspects of Disney can be indirectly related to the healthcare field too.

Indirect Association: Customer-First Ideology

While healthcare is an incredible thing that can save and improve the lives of so many people each day, it is certainly not a perfect system. One major reoccurring issue within society is racial and ethnic discrimination, and healthcare is no exception. Unfortunately, discrimination is prevalent within healthcare and this treatment towards individuals can become a determinant and barrier towards the care one receives. For example, in a study done by Cone Health's Wesley Long Cancer Center and the University of Pittsburgh Medical Center's Hillman Cancer Center, patients were randomly selected to be observed throughout their cancer journeys. The study took out factors such as marital status, patient's age, income, and health insurance and the results found that in both hospitals, black men and women were less likely to complete their treatment as opposed to the white patients. A black woman who did stay for the entirety of her treatment

was interviewed and spoke about the poor treatment she received and gave insights such as, “physicians didn’t take time to explain their diagnoses and options, front-desk staff who treated them with disrespect, and lack of support in dealing with complications” (Hostetter & Klein, 2018). The same study also highlighted another huge issue in healthcare that is amplified by race and ethnicity, which is that when many health screening tests were made to determine the presence of colorectal cancer, racial disparities arose. Only 43% of the patients who took the test were patients of color while 69.2% were white. After several interviews, it was found that the decrease in tests taken by patients of color stemmed from previous bad experiences with poor treatment and a lack of respect during the invasive screenings due to their race. The same study was done specifically looking at Latino and white patients and the Latino population screenings were also lower by 5% (Hostetter & Klein, 2018). Although 5 to 20% may not seem like a drastic difference, these studies work to represent the issue that a lack of proper healthcare prevention for potentially fatal diseases due to discrimination and poor treatment is present and rising.

Applicable Data

Similarly, during the interview portion of this research, I asked participants to answer the following question:

During the last time you received a healthcare service, did you experience any of the following: (Please select all that apply):

- Good, welcoming customer service**
- A clear/brief description of the service you were receiving**
- A lack of understanding about the procedures/policies being utilized**

-Any form of bias or discrimination

While the majority of the 80 participants selected that they had a good experience with welcoming service and a clear understanding of the service they would be receiving, 18 participants said that they experienced a lack of understanding about the service or policies that would be done and 8 said they experienced a form of bias or discrimination. While 10% may not seem like a high rate of discrimination, any percentage greater than 0 should be a cause for change.

Although my study had a smaller sample size, it supports the greater literature out there that discrimination and bias is present when patients are receiving the care they need.

In an additional select-all question, it was found that only 30.5% of participants do screening check-ups. Based on these statistics, I can conclude that while this low percentage may not explicitly be due to race or discrimination, it's clear that screening and preventive measures aren't welcoming or promoted enough to be more prevalent in our society and specifically within my community at Cal State Fullerton.

Although discrimination is an issue within healthcare, it doesn't have to be. This is one way in which we can learn from the work and policies that Disney has in place to indirectly improve healthcare. There are several avenues Disney takes to be more inclusive and customer centered. The Disney company takes pride in training its employees and cast members to be open and welcoming towards guests, even training them to direct and point with two fingers instead of one to remain respectful when giving directions. Disney not only envelops this respectful demeanor in its cast member training but also hosts events like the previously mentioned Gay Days and special events like 'Celebrate Soulfully' to commemorate Black History Month, to not

only respect but to celebrate diversity and uniqueness among the community (Baratti, 2022). Additionally, Disney recently updated its cast-member policies to allow and support its workers to show tattoos, have colorfully painted nails, and to have gender-neutral or colored hair (Gibson, K). It's steps and changes such as these ones that keep the Disney company accountable and updated in how to respect and support not only its guests, but its employees as well. If healthcare industries and platforms also took initiative to be more outward and inclusive by hosting extra trainings for healthcare professionals to learn or programs to be more respectful towards all individuals, it's possible that discrimination in the field could decrease.

Discrimination and patient-physician dynamic issues is a huge problem in healthcare that can't be fully changed overnight. However, taking small steps like extra training and really seeing healthcare as a patient-centered thing could really help. Based on the events, training, and policies in place, I truly believe that Disney strives and succeeds in being a customer-centered company majority of the time. Although the same cannot be said for healthcare right now, making changes and striving to be better could get the field to that point too. I believe that healthcare should adopt some of the customer-first ideologies and policies Disney ingrains in its cast members to be more inclusive and make medicine a little bit more magical for each patient.

Indirect Association: Consistency and Communication

Another issue that can sometimes be present within healthcare is inconsistency. Patient anxiety is typically considered a normal response when someone is experiencing illness or requires extra care; however, patient anxiety can also increase when patients don't know what to expect or how to be heard when receiving care. According to JAMA Network, some common sources of patient anxiety include sometimes having good experiences and sometimes bad ones

when receiving care and being unable to properly communicate or be heard by their healthcare providers (Shanafelt, Ripp, & Trockel, 2020). Unfortunately, with complicated terminology and countless people involved in the healthcare process, it can sometimes be difficult to communicate or fully comprehend the services a patient may be receiving. Not only that, but between issues like discrimination and complicated healthcare practices, the experiences patients may receive can become very inconsistent between good and bad.

Applicable Data

To better grasp these issues within this study, the following questions were asked to interviewees.

When receiving healthcare services (i.e. screenings, procedures, check-ups), how often do you feel nervous, anxious, or uncomfortable?

When answering this question, 20.7% of participants answered, “almost always”, 51.2% answered “about 50% of the time”, and 28% said almost never. These results indicate that the experience one receives is inconsistent and that the majority have some good and some bad experiences while receiving healthcare. While there may be several underlying factors into this trend, it’s possible that with more inclusive measures in place, better communication between physicians and patients, and a more welcoming environment and attitude from healthcare providers, these statistics could begin to shift.

In an additional select-all question, 22.5% of participants face a lack of understanding about the service that they will receive during their visit. This result also supports the previous literature cited that miscommunication or an inability to be heard while receiving care can lead to patient anxiety and thus contribute to those varying and inconsistent patient experience recounts.

With these results in mind, it can be seen that inconsistent experiences and a lack of communication or clarity can play a major role in the healthcare system from a patient's perspective. While the experiences at Disneyland may not always be perfect, based on our interview results from this project, we've seen that the majority of the time, customers are satisfied and happy with their experience. Once again, I believe that healthcare providers could take a page out of Disney's book to start modeling these same trends. One potential step in the right direction could be establishing better communication between physicians and patients. Disney is very modernized and ahead in society with its use of technology, especially the Disneyland app. While some healthcare providers utilize mobile apps and technology to communicate with patients, it can be challenging to know which physician to message or where to find and interpret medical records. Thus, it's important to have strong customer service at the ready to assist patients in an online capacity as Disney's customer service successfully does. An additional solution could be training in being consistent with all patients. As mentioned previously, by receiving training similar to Disney cast members, healthcare providers can learn techniques to be more inclusive and welcoming while doing their jobs. By adopting these practices and ingraining them early on in careers, that consistency in work ethic and impact will follow and become a byproduct. Not only that, but an increase in consistency and comfort for patients might encourage more individuals to seek preventative measures, like health screenings, and to reach out for help earlier on, therefore bettering the health of those in our society along the way, too.

Between both indirect associations that have been discussed thus far, establishing Disney practices like worker training could make an incredible impact early on. While healthcare workers already receive extensive training on being strong medical professions, by focusing

more on customer or patient-first techniques as Disney does, it could potentially better patient experiences and develop greater consistency and communication within the field as a whole.

Indirect Association: Community Establishment

As seen in previous interview analysis, it can be concluded that the majority of participants only go see their healthcare professionals when they're sick and truly need to. While this isn't detrimental to health, it definitely decreases the amount of preventative healthcare being made and limits the strong and healthy connections between physicians and patients.

One area that Disney is very strong in is its community and family. Disney does a great job establishing a community by being consistent and making accessible outlets for people to find the magic, such as Disney+ and its social media presence, that allows these services to be more accessible. For example, the Disney Company does a great job getting out in the community to serve and their presence is extremely recognizable. When people see Mickey Mouse, the majority of individuals can make the association that Mickey Mouse is Disney. I believe that if healthcare was more consistent and ensured that patients had set primary care physicians, specialists, and other professionals backing them, patients may be able to make those same associations that they do with Mickey and Disney. Extra outreach efforts and communication could establish a baseline that when individuals see their doctors or read emails with their dentist's name that they recognize, they know that it's their healthcare professional who makes them feel better and are reaching out to give care. The consistency and community that Disney has built allows these associations to be inherently ingrained in many people. If healthcare did the same and was more organized to ensure that when possible, and starting at young ages, folks could see the same doctors and same people consistently, there may be less

anxiety associated with health-related procedures. While these practices are already present in some healthcare providers, it's not in others. I think striving to get this feature to be uniformly present across the board in numerous healthcare providers, and not just private practices or Kaiser, would really help. For example, and as a personal account, I go to the same optometry office whenever I need to get my eye exams done and each time, I see a different optometrist. If someone in this same situation was nervous or anxious about getting an eye exam, seeing a familiar face who has positively helped them before could really help reduce that anxiety and make a big difference in how that individual views optometrists as a whole. These connections and sense of community not only make healthcare more welcoming but more accessible too.

While healthcare doesn't have fun characters like Mickey and Minnie and doesn't have streaming platforms like Disney+, it can make strides in turning each patient's healthcare professional into their own Mickey and their own easily recognizable magic-maker. Healthcare industries can make similar efforts like those made for Disney+ to make healthcare services more accessible, especially in an online format. Whether it be to easily make appointments, do virtual visits, or a simple check-up email, these small changes could make a huge difference in accessibility and to potentially reduce patient anxieties and negative experiences too. While healthcare industries can't replicate Disney's work, it can adopt similar principles to bring even just a little more magic into the healthcare field.

Conclusion

I have always loved anything and everything Disney-related. I have also appreciated and been infatuated with medicine for my entire life and consider helping others while in a healthcare field my passion and purpose for life. However, I will be the first to admit that the healthcare system is not perfect. With medicine and healthcare industries doing life-changing work each and every day, it also contains several barriers and constraints to other lives at the same time.

The purpose of this research was not to suggest that all healthcare industries and companies become Disney-themed or suddenly place roller coasters and theme park rides in their lobbies- though that would be pretty amazing. The purpose of this research was to analyze and identify the aspects of the Disney company that make it so special and effective at bringing people joy and to find the nooks and crannies within the healthcare system where some of those Disney aspects could apply.

The three most important themes identified in this research that allows Disney to be so magical are their customer-first ideology, their consistency and communication, and their community establishment. Whether these aspects stem from the theme parks, community appearances, or the animation studio, they are the backbone for this company that makes it undeniably influential. Instead of adopting roller coasters, delicious amusement park food, or movie content, the healthcare industry and the professionals within it could begin adopting these backbone aspects to begin building a better system. Discrimination, inaccessibility, and poor experiences run rampant within the healthcare system. While the system cannot change overnight, changes and adaptations can be made to begin the gradual change and movement towards better and more magical care.

Similar to how my research has shown that Disney is not just magical because of the things it provides, but because of the people providing it, healthcare could be the same too. My proposed suggestions should start with our healthcare professionals, past, present, and future. Our doctors, optometrists, dentists, veterinarians, and every healthcare professional in between should become the cast members of their offices. They should be given the training and resources to be more consistently impactful, to be the best communicators they can be, to be involved in the community, and to be patient-centered.

Our healthcare system will never be perfect, and neither will the Disney company, because nothing ever is. However, Disney provides a strong framework for the type of company and service that makes a positive difference and impact. Applying these same themes and blueprints to healthcare could truly make a difference, save a life, and create a healthier society as a whole. So, I propose that we assemble as the superhero professionals that we strive to be, make Mickey and Minnie proud, and work each and every day to make our work just a little bit more impactful and magical, too.

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Appendix

Interview Questions

Disney Related Questions

1. Have you ever been to any of the Disneyland Parks?
2. If you have been to the Disneyland Parks before, which of the following aspects positively contributed to your time there?
 - a. Character Experience (Meet and Greets, Parades, Shows, etc.)
 - b. Attractions/Rides
 - c. Customer Service of Cast Members
 - d. Overall Theme Park Environment(Park Layout, Design, Music, Smell, etc.)
3. Which of the following do you believe contributes most positively to the Disney Company overall?
 - a. Disney+
 - b. Disney Animation Studio(characters, movies, etc.)
 - c. Disneyland Theme Parks
 - d. The Customer Service/Policies of the Company
4. Please select all of the following that apply to you.
 - a. Have visited a Disneyland theme park
 - b. Have streamed off of the Disney+ service
 - c. Has a favorite Disney character/movie
5. In general, how strongly do you believe customer service plays a role in your experience in any activity or at any place?
 - a. Scale of 0 to 5, 0 being not important at all and 5 being extremely important

6. From the times you have utilized a service from the Disney franchise, how often did you have a positive experience?
 - a. Almost never
 - b. About 50% of the time
 - c. Almost always

Healthcare Related Questions

7. Have you been to see a healthcare professional (doctor, dentist, optometrist, etc.) within the last year?
8. When receiving healthcare services (i.e. screenings, procedures, check-ups), how often do you feel nervous, anxious, or uncomfortable?
 - a. Almost never
 - b. About 50% of the time
 - c. Almost always
9. Please select any of the following statements that apply to you.
 - a. I receive health screenings on a regular basis to prevent getting sick
 - b. I only go to healthcare providers when I am sick or need to
 - c. I try to avoid the doctor/dental offices as much as possible
10. During the last time you received a healthcare service, did you experience any of the following? Please select all that apply.
 - a. Good, welcoming customer service
 - b. A clear debrief/description of the service you were receiving
 - c. A lack of understanding about the procedures/policies being utilized
 - d. Any form of bias or discrimination